

SYNTHESIS OF SUBSTITUTED AROYLBENZOFURANS. PART I

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Several chloro-arylbenzofurans have been synthesised by the Rap reaction, using *o*-hydroxyketones.

Several arylbenzofurans were prepared by Schraufstütter and Deutsch (*Z. Naturforsch.*, 1949, 46, 276) for their therapeutic evaluation. Closely related heterocycles of the type of isoflavones and isoflavons have been observed by Bradbury and White (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 3447; 1953, 871) to possess estrogenic activity. Coumarins also have been found to possess estrogenic activity by Gley and Mentzer (*Compt. rend. Soc. Biol.*, 1945, 139, 1055).

These investigations and the close similarity among isoflavens, isoflavones, coumarins and the benzofurans, led Bisagni, Butt Hoi and Royer (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 3688, 3693) to synthesise a number of 2-arylbenzofurans and related compounds, and some of these compounds showed estrogenic activity.

The present investigation was therefore undertaken to synthesise a number of chloro-arylbenzofurans, with a view to studying their therapeutic value.

The method used for the preparation of the 2-arylbenzofurans is that of Rap (*Gazzetta*, 1895, 25, 285), where the potassium salt of a suitably substituted *o*-hydroxyketone is condensed with a substituted bromoacetophenone. The reaction can be represented as:

The easy availability of the *o*-hydroxyketones through the Fries rearrangement of phenolic esters, and the comparative ease with which the Rap reaction could be effected, led us to follow the same synthesis. The *o*-hydroxyketones were obtained by the Fries rearrangement of acetates, propionates and butyrates of *o*-chloro- and 2:4-dichlorophenols. The esters were obtained in over 90% yield by using the method of Chattaway (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2495) and were pure enough for the Fries migration. The Fries rearrangement of the acetate, propionate and butyrate of 2:4-dichlorophenol has already been reported in the literature (Chien and Yin, *Chem. Abs.*, 1940, 34, 1979), whereas the rearrangement of the corresponding esters of *o*-chlorophenol has been effected for the first time.

Phenacyl bromide and *p*-chlorophenacyl bromide, required in the synthesis, were obtained by the bromination of acetophenone and *p*-chloroacetophenone respectively, in glacial acetic acid (Reid, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 41, 771).

The 2-arylbenzofurans were characterised through their oximes, excepting in the case of 3-methyl-7-chloro-2-*p*-chlorobenzoyl-benzofuran, which was characterised through its semicarbazone.

TABLE I

S. No.	Benzofuran.	M.P.	% Carbon. Found, Calc.	% Hydrogen. Found, Calc.	Colour developed Benzofuran & conc. H ₂ SO ₄ .	M.P.	($\times$) in e Found.	Calc.
A.	3-Methyl-5:7-dichloro-2-benzoyl-	145°	62.26 62.94	3.27 3.28	Deep brown yellow	198°	C: 59.60 H: 3.40 N: 4.20	60.00% 3.44 4.38
B.	3-Methyl-5:7-dichloro-2- <i>p</i> -chloro- benzoyl-	218°	56.02 56.56	2.61 2.65	Reddish brown yellow	195°	C: 53.85 H: 2.41 N: 3.80	54.16 2.82 3.95
C.	3-Ethyl-5:7-dichloro-2-benzoyl-	90°	63.24 63.84	3.34 3.76	Yellow	137°	C: 60.76 H: 3.24 N: 4.20	61.08 3.89 4.13
D.	3-Ethyl-3:7-dichloro-2- <i>p</i> -chloro- benzoyl-	135°	57.01 57.7	2.92 3.11	Red	162°	C: 54.76 H: 3.11 N: 3.65	55.36 3.26 3.80
E.	3-Propyl-5:7-dichloro-2-benzoyl-	93°	64.12 64.87	4.11 4.20	Red	130°	C: 61.95 H: 4.29 N: 4.12	62.07 4.31 4.02
F.	3-Propyl-5:7-dichloro-2- <i>p</i> -chloro- benzoyl-	135°	58.15 58.78	3.26 3.54	Red	160°	C: 56.20 H: 3.01 N: 3.64	56.46 3.66 3.66
G.	3-Methyl-7-chloro-2-benzoyl-	110°	69.92 70.98	3.92 4.06	Deep reddish brown	157°	C: 67.02 H: 4.02 N: 4.85	67.24 4.21 4.90
H.	3-Ethyl-7-chloro-2- <i>p</i> -chloro- benzoyl-	140°	62.20 62.94	3.25 3.28	Very dark reddish brown	190°*	C: 55.86* H: 3.23* N: 11.45*	56.35* 3.59* 11.60*
I.	3-Ethyl-7-chloro-2-benzoyl-	80°	71.30 71.70	4.20 4.57	Orange	134°	C: 67.75 H: 4.15 N: 4.63	68.11 4.67 4.47
J.	3-Ethyl-7-chloro-2- <i>p</i> -chloro- benzoyl-	114°	63.11 63.94	3.41 3.76	Red	147°	C: 60.82 H: 3.34 N: 4.21	61.08 3.89 4.19
K.	3-Propyl-7-chloro-2-benzoyl-	82°	69.98 72.38	5.01 5.02	Yellow	145°	C: 68.27 H: 5.01 N: 4.09	68.91 5.10 4.11
L.	3-Propyl-7-chloro-2- <i>p</i> -chloro- benzoyl-	130°	64.23 64.87	4.01 4.20	Violet	151°	C: 61.73 H: 4.11 N: 3.61	62.07 4.31 3.35

* Of semicarbazone.

Some of the benzofurans, prepared by Buu Hoi *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) have been found to give a red halochromy with concentrated sulphuric acid. Most of the compounds reported in this paper have also responded to this test.

EXPERIMENTA

Preparation of the Esters.—The phenol (1 mole) was dissolved in NaOH solution (1.5 moles, 50 c.c.) and mixed with crushed ice (600 g.) and cooled externally by ice. The appropriate acid anhydride (1.25 moles) (acetic, propionic or butyric) was quickly added and the mixture vigorously shaken for a few seconds. After separation of the ester a 10% NaOH solution (20 c.c.) was added and shaken again. It was extracted with ether, the ether extract was washed first with dilute caustic soda, then with water, dried over anhydrous calcium chloride and the ether removed. The yields in the case of 2:4-dichloro- and *o*-chloro-phenyl butyrate were nearly 100%. In all other cases it was over 90%. The esters were used directly for the Fries rearrangement.

2-Hydroxy-3-chloroacetophenone.—Anhydrous aluminium chloride (30 g.) was added to *o*-chlorophenyl acetate (32.7 g.) in a flask provided with a calcium chloride guard tube, and heated in an oil-bath for 2 hours at 110°. The reaction product was decomposed with HCl (dil.). The crude 2-hydroxy-3-chloroacetophenone was filtered and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 84°, yield 13 g. (40%). It responds to Pyman's test. (Found: C, 56.01; H, 4.02. $C_8H_7O_2Cl$ requires C, 56.31; H, 4.11%). Semicarbazone, m.p. 196°.

2-Hydroxy-3-chloropropiophenone.—The method followed was the same as above. The crude 2-hydroxy-3-chloropropiophenone was crystallised from aqueous alcohol as a yellow solid, m.p. 72°, yield 35%. The compound responds to Pyman's test. (Found: C, 58.12; H, 4.32. $C_9H_9O_2Cl$ requires C, 58.53; H, 4.88%). Semicarbazone, m.p. 130°.

2-Hydroxy-3-chlorobutyrophenone was prepared by the usual method, but it was found that by increasing the reaction time from 2 to 4 hours, the yield of the *o*-hydroxyketone increased from 17 to 36.5%. Recrystallised from alcohol, it melts at 118° and responds to Pyman's test. (Found: C, 59.92; H, 5.12. $C_{10}H_{11}O_2Cl$ requires C, 60.45; H, 5.54%). Semicarbazone, m.p. 142°.

Benzofurans.—*o*-Hydroxyketone (1 mole) was added to 1.25 moles of caustic potash dissolved in sufficient ethanol. To this was added phenacyl bromide (1 mole) and the mixture refluxed for 2½ to 4 hours. The alcohol was distilled off and water added to the cooled residue. The crude product was filtered and recrystallised from alcohol (or acetic acid in certain cases).

Oxime & Semicarbazone.—To the benzofuran (0.5 g.), dissolved in sufficient 95% ethanol, were added hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1 g.) and pyridine (1 c.c.), and refluxed for 2 hours. Most of the alcohol was then distilled off, and to the residue water was added gradually to precipitate the oxime. It was filtered, washed with hot water and crystallised from alcohol.

The semicarbazone was prepared likewise using semicarbazide hydrochloride instead of hydroxylamine hydrochloride in the above method.